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Chemical Examination of the Seeds of *Cassia laevigata*

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FROM the hot ethanolic extract of the seeds of *Cassia laevigata* two anthraquinones, chrysophanol (I) and physcion(II) and a flavonoid, quercetin 3,7-di-rhamnopyranoside(III) have been isolated and studied.

Compound (I), m.p. 195°, $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$, has been shown to be 1,8-di-hydroxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone (chrysophanol) and compound (II) m.p. 207°, $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ characterised as 1,8-di-hydroxy-6-methoxy-3-methyl-anthraquinone (physcion), by analysis, colour reactions, spectral data, degradation studies and derivatization.

The third compound m.p. 190° (d), $C_{27}H_{20}O_{17}$, on hydrolysis gave quercetin ($C_{15}H_{10}O_7$) and rhamnose. The position of the rhamnose units have been shown to be with the 3- and 7-hydroxyls by colour reactions¹ and spectral shift^{2,3}. The rhamnose units are present in the pyranose form as proved by periodate oxidation⁴ and the glycosidic linkages as α -, confirmed by its hydrolysis with takadiastase.

All the three compounds are known to occur in plants particularly in the genus *Cassia*.

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N-Acridin-5-yl-N'-Aryloxyacetyl Hydrazines as Possible Fungicides

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ALTHOUGH an unsubstituted nucleus containing heterocyclic nitrogen is seldom fungitoxic, acridine is known to be toxic to spores of various rusts¹. Horsfall and Rich² found acridine to be fairly active against *Sclerotinia fructicola* and *Macrosporium sarcinaeforme*. Acridines have been found to act as insecticides³⁻⁵, fungicides^{2,6}, bactericides⁷, medicinal⁸ and carcinogenic⁹ compounds.

We have therefore synthesised N-acridin-5-yl-N'-aryloxyacetyl hydrazines and screened some of them for their fungicidal activity against *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae*.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

N-Acridin-5-yl-N'-aryloxyacetyl hydrazines(I) :

A methanolic solution of a substituted-5-chloro-acridine¹⁰ (0.002 M) and an aryloxy acetyl hydrazine¹¹ (0.002 M) was refluxed gently for three hrs and cooled. The product separating out was filtered and recrystallised.

The compounds thus prepared, have been listed in Table 1.

Fungicidal Activity :

Twenty-one of these compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *A. flavus* and *H. oryzae* by agar plate technique¹² and found to be moderately active. The most active compounds were found to contain a naphthoxy ring. A change in the position of ethoxy group did not show any effect towards antifungal activity. Halogenated compounds possessed a bit higher fungicidal activity.